

DETAILED CHARACTERIZATION AND PRODUCT SPECIFICATION REPORT

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Work package in charge: WP5: Development of a prototype Operational Service

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

The AQ-WATCH will develop a supply chain leading to the generation of seven innovative downstream products and services for improving air quality forecasts and source attribution. These prototypes will be based on existing space and in situ observations of air quality and tailored to the identified needs of international users. **These innovative products and services are aimed at improving public health and optimizing renewable energy in different regions of the world.**

The capabilities of these products and services will be demonstrated in three different regions of the world in order to establish their potential for their widespread adoption beyond the lifetime of the project (USA, Chile, China). These services will be co-designed, tested, and evaluated in a joint effort with the prime users. Further feedback from the prime users on the operation of these products and services will lead to improved prototype products/services. **Here, we present the first version of these seven products,** however this first version will be modified according to the user’s input.

The Spiral Process. AQ-WATCH will develop dynamic interactions between the developers of the prototype products/services and the prime users in 3 regions of the world. The process (Figure 1) by which value is added to space and in situ data will be modulated by the input of these users and will involve successive iterations during which feedback reactions will be collected and analysed, and included in the new development. This spiral approach from the original data to marketable products is schematically represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Illustration of the spiral process to gather successive feedbacks from the prime users during the development phase of the prototype products and services.

2. Conclusion & Results

Not relevant

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
[1] To design and produce new global and regional air pollution atlases that include the climatological distribution of chemical pollutants complemented by quantities such as the diurnal and seasonal variations, air quality and related health indices, premature mortality exceedance frequency, long-term trends, etc.	Yes
[2] To develop software packages with the capability to provide more accurate daily forecasts of air quality at the regional scale including tailored high-resolution fire smoke and wind-blown dust forecasts; downscaling of air quality forecasts to 2 km resolution in urban areas.	Yes
[3] To develop a source apportionment service to mitigate air pollution and hence increase the life expectancy of the population in different regions of the world, with special focus on the role of agricultural sources of air pollution and the potentially important effects of fracking operations.	Yes
[4] To develop a new tool-box that will be user-friendly and accessible to decision-makers to evaluate the efficiency of proposed mitigation measures in different industrial sectors on the resulting level of air pollutants in three different regions of the world. This will establish the basis for their wider adoption and generalization.	Yes
[5] To co-design, co-produce, and co-evaluate for the first-time prototype products and services with prime users in three regions of the world chosen for their specific level of economic, social, and environmental development.	Yes

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This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Packages.

Objectives of WP1	Relevance in this deliverable?
1.1 Identification of the User's Needs and elaboration of the User Requirement Document	Yes
1.2 Identification of Improved Products based on Users' feedbacks	No
1.3 Identification of the final products for commercialisation consistently with the business model	No

Objectives of WP2	Relevance in this deliverable?
2.1 Preparation of an air-quality dataset using satellite data downloaded from the WEkEO DIAS (Copernicus Data and Information Access Services). WEkEO is still under development: before it is fully operational, the data will be accessed through the Copernicus Atmosphere Data Store (available in July 2019) and through the Sentinel Hub EO browser (sentinel-hub.com/explore.eobrowser). The Copernicus Atmosphere Service retrospective reanalysis will also be accessed through WEkEO. As soon as all the observations are available in WEkEO, all data used in the project will be accessed through this system, complemented by third-party data for parameters not covered by Copernicus.	Yes
2.2 Develop an atlas including visualization of satellite and in-situ data as well as air pollution maps to assist monitoring and analyses of air pollution.	Yes
2.3 Use of satellite, surface observations, and the CAMS reanalysis to provide global and regional climatologies of air pollution including statistical information (means, diurnal and seasonal variability, long-term trends, exceedances)	Yes
2.4 Develop an innovative method to calculate health indices and mortality from outdoor pollution using satellite observations	Yes

Objectives of WP3	Relevance in this deliverable?
3.1 To develop a harmonized set of detailed AQ forecast and alert systems for the focus regions: US Colorado State, Chile, Beijing Urban Area and BTH (Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei) area with possibility of expansion to other regions	Yes
3.2 To develop the tailored fire and fire smoke forecasting services targeting the focus regions	Yes
3.3 To develop the tailored wind-blown dust services targeting the focus regions	Yes
3.4 To establish the near-real-time evaluation of the developed services using the operationally available satellite and in-situ data	Yes

Objectives of WP4	Relevance in this deliverable?
4.1 To establish a user driven service for (NRT) source apportionment information	Yes
4.2 To establish a user driven service for mitigation information on most effective emission reduction measures	Yes
4.3 To establish a fracking service for the assessment of the impact of fracking activities on air pollution	Yes
4.4 To improve the quality of the above mentioned three services, through validation, customization and targeted developments	Yes

Objectives of WP5	Relevance in this deliverable?
5.1 Release the developed applications for web and mobile air quality toolkit, targeted to air quality managers and to the public.	Yes
5.2 Enable an easy access to warning systems to allow individuals exposed to air pollution to take preventive measures, which could reduce health impacts and healthcare costs from adverse effects of air pollution.	Yes
5.3 Give an access to personalized information or variability forecast to help individuals manage their life. Users will be able to use tools to search locations, view personal exposures, or exposure reduction over time. The AQ-WATCH tools will allow individuals to navigate and choose outdoor places to live, work, go to school, shop, travel, exercise, plan activities ahead and better manage treatments. The system will allow patients' physicians access to air quality information, which should enhance disease management and medical decisions.	Yes
5.4 Introduce behavioural changes through air quality alerts (push notifications) with thresholds to be defined in accordance with national or local regulation, in coordination with local authorities.	Yes
5.5 Allow a better location of air quality issues, which represents a key value for healthcare professionals and policy-makers to better locate and enhance prevention for communities at risk.	Yes

Objectives of WP6	Relevance in this deliverable?
<p>6.1 To work with prime users in Colorado, Chile and China on the implementation and development of the proposed prototype products and services.</p> <p>The pilot implementations will include Denver/Colorado, Santiago/Chile and BTH (Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei) /China, each region experiencing different AQ issues and different air quality policies and management structure so as to develop a tool that is applicable to a wide range of users.</p>	Yes

AQ-WATCH Deliverable

6.2 To release the developed web and mobile AQ toolkit to air quality managers and the public.	Yes
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Objectives of WP7	Relevance in this deliverable?
7.1 Clustering with major EU and international projects and initiatives relevant for the project to guarantee the use of available knowledge (state-of-the-art);	No
7.2 Establishing contact with potential international end-users by building a community interested and capable to make the best use of the project results;	Yes
7.3 Providing information and technological briefings to the competent authorities to make them aware of project results;	Yes
7.4 Providing support for standardization activities;	No
7.5 Preparing the AQ-WATCH Plan for Use and Dissemination of Foreground Knowledge;	No
7.6 Develop business cases in the regions of the world of the pilot-cases.	No

Objectives of WP8	Relevance in this deliverable?
8.1 Project management: Facilitating governance and strategic decision-making through project committees, boards, management procedures, and project management tools, performing technical, financial and contract management of the consortium, establishing and maintaining an effective working relationship between AQ-WATCH and the European Commission (EC).	No
8.2 Day-to-day scientific and innovation coordination: Carrying out the overall coordination necessary for reaching the scientific and innovation objectives, and elaborating research risk management.	No
8.3 Data management: Establishing data management linked to the Copernicus system (DIAS) at project level, fostering transparency and the promotion of data and meta-data standards, implementing open access data policies.	No
8.4 Implementing the innovation management, support dissemination and communication activities: Coordinating innovation management and monitoring the IPR relevant issues. Supporting WP6 and WP7 to deliver dedicated communication tools and materials, tailored dissemination and communication activities, and promotion of AQ-WATCH Toolkit and marketable products towards stakeholders and customers in several regions of the world outside Europe.	No

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

This deliverable includes a detailed description and specifications of the seven products which are going to be developed by the AQ-WATCH project. The following products are going to be developed during the project:

(1) Global and regional atlases of air quality indices and reports. Graphical and numerical information on the regional climatology of air pollutants based on satellite information including air quality indices and health indices (e.g., premature mortality); Production of a global atlas of air quality with regional graphical information.

(2) Daily forecasts of air quality for metropolitan areas. Daily forecast of air pollution at the regional scale based on an ensemble of predictive models as well as satellite and ground-based information.

(3) Dust and solar energy forecasts. Predictions of the degradation of air quality and reduction in visibility caused by dust mobilization and impact on solar energy systems.

(4) Wildfire and Visibility Service. Predictions of the degradation of air quality and reduction in visibility caused by the occurrence of wildfires and the development of a related regional alert system.

(5) Information service about air pollution resulting from fracking operations. Model predictions of the potential impact on regional air quality (e.g., ozone levels) due to fracking operations and determination of the exposure of the local population to related emissions of hydrocarbons.

(6) Attribution service with focus on agricultural sources. Information on the attribution of emission sources for different economic sectors with emphasis on the role of agricultural emissions.

(7) Emission mitigation service. Development of a demonstration model to allow future customers to assess the efficiency of alternative actions to mitigate air pollution. Development of strategy options for air pollution abatement and support of air quality policy.

Since the technology and the layout of some of these products has clear similarities, it has been decided to combine some of these products in the format of modules as described below:

- **Module 1** - Air quality world atlas - an AQ map of the world which allows the users to understand and research the historical, current, and forecasted AQ statistics in a specific area, both globally and regionally, including daily forecast of air pollution at the regional scale (product 1 and 2).
- **Module 2** - Air quality attribution & mitigation - the purpose of this module is to provide information on various sources of pollution and simulate potential changes in air quality in response to changes in emissions (product 6 and 7).

- **Module 3** - Dust and fire forecasting - the purpose of this module is to provide information on dust storm forecast and accumulation, as well as predictions of the degradation of air quality and reduction in visibility caused by the occurrence of wildfires (products 3 and 4).
- **Module 4** - Fracking analysis - the purpose of this module is to provide information on the expected release and dispersion of pollution as a result of fracking activities (product 5)

4.1. General System layout

The user will be able to examine all products on the same website by switching between the different modules tabs as demonstrated below

4.2. Modules specification

4.2.1. Module 1 - The global and regional atlas

An air quality map of the world which allows the users to understand and research the historical, current, and forecasted AQ statistics in a specific area. This module includes: Global and regional atlases of air quality indices and reports. Graphical and numerical information on the regional climatology of air pollutants based on the Copernicus CAMS global and regional reanalyses, which are constrained by satellite information. Daily forecasts of air quality for metropolitan areas will also be included in the atlas.

4.2.1.1. Specification of the global atlas

- **Grid resolution:**
 - 0.8°x0.8°
- **Countries available for the AQ atlas statistics:**
 - All countries of the world in addition to states/provinces for the largest countries (USA, Canada, Russia, China and India)
 - As indicated above, potentially grouping countries (e.g., the 26 and 40 groups used in the IPCC/UNFCCC reports)
- **Pollutant types and types of AQ information:**
 - from the CAMS global reanalysis: NO₂, SO₂, O₃, CO, BC, OC, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀
 - from satellite: Aerosol optical depth (AOD)
 - from satellite: NO₂ (Tropospheric column)
- **Data refresh rate:**
 - Every 3 months
- **Type of data:**
 - Historical

- **Historical timeframe (i.e., how far back can the model be run for the different time resolutions).**
 - For surface data:
Yearly: 2003-2018
Monthly: 2003-2018
Weekly: 2003-2018
Daily: for the last month available
Seasonal data: 2003-2018
 - Satellite data:
MODIS AOD:
Yearly, seasonal, monthly, daily: 2002-present

Merged AOD:
Yearly: 1995-2017
Monthly: 2002-2018
Weekly: 2002-2018
Daily: for the last month available
Seasonal data: 2002-2018.
- **Parameter to be presented on a country level:**
Gridded population
- **Data sources**
 - CAMS global reanalysis (temporal resolution: 6 hours)
 - MODIS Collection 6.1 AOD data will be uploaded with 1-2 days delay for daily data and at the beginning of the next month for monthly data. Seasonal and yearly means will be calculated when the corresponding input (monthly) data are available.
1°x 1° resolution daily AOD
1°x 1° resolution monthly AOD

4.2.1.2. Specification of the regional atlas

- **Regional Availability:** Chile, Colorado (USA), Beijing (China)
- **Product availability:** Front range, Colorado
- **Grid resolution**
 - 0.1°
- **Pollutant types**
 - NO₂, SO₂, O₃, PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀
- **Data refresh rate**
 - Daily
- **Type of data**
 - Historical and Forecast

- **Historical timeframe**

- Yearly: 2014-2018
 - Seasonal: 2014-2018
 - Monthly: 2014-2018
 - Weekly: 2014-2018
 - Daily: for the last month available

- **Forecast timeframe:**

- 96-hour forecast (hourly data)

- **Data sources:**

- CAMS regional reanalysis
 - Monitoring AQ data (at least for the three AQ-WATCH regions)
 - SILAM, LOTOS-EUROS (for the forecasts)
 - Satellite AOD:
 - MODIS Collection 6.1 AOD data with possible 1-day delay
 - 3km*3km resolution daily AOD
 - 10km*10km resolution daily AOD

Daily AOD can be refreshed every day, if available; monthly AOD is available on NASA LAADS a few days after the end of the month.

NO₂ Tropospheric Column

NO₂ TROPOMI satellite data will be oversampled to a finer grid (e.g. 1 km), once the grid size is defined

For this finer grid temporal averaging periods should be longer than one day; yearly, monthly, and weekly. Note that TROPOMI data starts from 2018, so the historical perspective cannot be done using this instrument.

4.2.1.3. Data provision

For this module, Working Package 2 (WP2) is responsible for providing the satellite, model, and in-situ data. The provision of regional forecast data is responsibility of WP3.

4.2.2. Module 2 - Air Quality Mitigation

The purpose of this module is to provide information on various sources of air pollution and simulate potential changes in air quality in response to proposed mitigation strategies (e.g.: agriculture, industrial sectors, natural sources, Sector and country contribution to air quality). This module enables the user to conduct emission mitigation by modelling demonstration of the efficiency of alternative actions to mitigate air pollution.

4.2.2.1. Module 2 specification

- **Regional availability: Chile, Colorado, Beijing**
- **Grid resolution**
 - Santiago (Chile): 0.05°x0.025°, ~5kmx3km

- Front Range Colorado: ~12km (in future 4 km)
- Xicheng district, Beijing, China: 2km x 2 km
- **Product availability:**
 - Santiago
 - Front Range Colorado,
 - Mitigation for China will be added later.
- **Pollutant types:**
 - PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, CO (only Colorado), O₃ (Colorado and Beijing), at a later stage SO₂ and health index
- **Data refresh rate:**
 - Daily
- **Model availability**
 - Attribution will be done for past 6 weeks
- **Type of data**
 - Historical and simulation
 - Forecast (for CO in Colorado and for Beijing)
- **Historical timeframe:**
 - 6 weeks, daily attributions
- **Forecast timeframe:**
 - 2-day attribution forecasts for 3-hourly CO for Colorado front range
 - 4-day forecasts for 1-hourly PM_{2.5} and O₃ for Beijing with mitigation service
- **Country contributors to the city level:**
 - Santiago: Chile, all South American countries separately, outside South America, boundary
 - Colorado front range PM/NO₂: Colorado, Wyoming, Nebraska, Kansas, Utah, Arizona, Texas, New Mexico, Oklahoma, Other US, Canada, Mexico, other, boundary
 - Colorado front range CO: Denver urban area, OG area, non-Colorado states, boundary, Asia
- **Country contributors to the grid level:**
 - same as above
- **Sector contributors to the city level:**
 - Santiago-Colorado PM/NO₂: agriculture, residential combustion, road traffic, non-road traffic, power plants, industry, (copper smelters, if in emission database), mining and extraction, wildfires, marine, dust, boundary
 - Front range Colorado CO: anthropogenic, fires, chemical, boundary, Boundary fires
 - Beijing (PM, O₃, NO₂): traffic, industry, residential
- **Sector contributors to the grid level:**
 - same as above
- **Describe the data sources**
 - LOTOS-EUROS
 - WRF-CHEM
 - CHIMERE-SIRANE
 - BOXMOX/MUSICBOX

4.2.2.2. Data provision

For this module, WP4 is responsible for providing the model source apportionment data.

4.2.3. Module 3 - Dust and Fires Forecasting

4.2.3.1. Specification of the dust product

The purpose of this module is to provide information on dust storm forecast, dust accumulation and solar energy. This product aims to help dust and solar energy forecasts, by predictions of the degradation of air quality and reduction in visibility caused by dust mobilization and impact on solar energy systems.

- **Forecast time resolution:**
 - Hourly data
- **Forecast Data refresh rate**
 - Daily
- **How far ahead does the model go?**
 - 3-day forecast (72 hours)
- **Countries/cities availability / Grid level**
 - Beijing: 72°E – 128°E; 26°N – 52°N
 - Colorado: 124°W – 102°W; 25°N – 46°N
 - Chile: 78°W – 60°W; 36°S – 12°S
- **Grid resolution:**
 - 0.2°x02°
- **Product parameters for forecast data:**
 - Dust products:
 - AOD (Aerosol Optical Depth)
 - Surface concentrations (PM10 and PM2.5)
 - Dust deposition (PM10 and PM2.5)
 - Visibility
 - Solar energy products:
 - DNI (Direct Normal Irradiance)
 - GHI (Global Horizontal Irradiation)
 - Soiling: To be studied for Chile as a function of:
 - Observations available
 - Interactions with prime user
 - Performance of model in reproducing available observations

- **Data sources :**

	Colorado, USA	Santiago, Chile	Beijing, China
SILAM & IS4FIRES / FMI	0.1° global SILAM dust	0.1° global SILAM dust	0.1° global SILAM dust
MONARCH / BSC	0.2°	0.2°	0.2°
WRF-Chem, MOZART, MOSAIC / MPI			MarcoPolo-Panda, 0.25°
Lotos-Euros / TNO			MarcoPolo-Panda, 0.25°
WRF-Chem & WACCM / UCAR	4 km		
CHIMERE / BMILP & INERIS			25km China, 2km Beijing
CHIMERE / UCHILE		0.1° dust own	

4.2.3.2. Specification of the fire product

The purpose of this module is to provide information on fire forecast and historical data

This module will provide wildfire and visibility service, by predictions of the degradation of air quality and reduction in visibility caused by the occurrence of wildfires and the development of a related regional alert system.

- **Global grid resolution:**
 - 0.2°
 - in China: 0.125°
- **Type of data:**
 - Historical and Forecast
- **Historical time resolution:**
 - Hourly data
- **Forecast time resolution:**
 - Hourly data
- **Historical data refresh rate:**
 - Daily

- **Forecast Data refresh rate**
 - Daily
- **Model data availability**
 - 2000
- **Forecast window**
 - 96 hours
- **Product parameters for forecast data**
 - PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, AOD, at the second stage - smoke toxic components, such as PAH
- **Product parameters for historical data**
 - same as for historical data
- **Data sources**

	Colorado, USA	Santiago, Chile	Beijing, China
SILAM & IS4FIRES / FMI	0.1° IS4FIRES + GFAS	0.1 ° IS4FIRES + GFAS	0.1 ° IS4FIRES+ GFAS
WRF-Chem, MOZART, MOSAIC / MPI		0.1 ° GFAS	MarcoPolo-Panda, 0.25 °
Lotos-Euros / TNO			MarcoPolo-Panda, 0.25 °
WRF-Chem & WACM / UCAR	4 km, FINN & QFED		

UCAR can provide WRF-Chem 2-day forecasts at 12km over CONUS (4 km over Colorado will be available within the next few months) of CO tracers for fires within CONUS and from outside CONUS. Output is hourly, output is archived starting May 2019. These simulations use FINN NRT emissions.

On the global scale UCAR can provide WACCM 10-day forecasts at 1o spatial resolution, which also include a CO Fire tracer. WACMM simulations are driven by two different fire inventories (FINN and QFED). Output is 6-hourly.

See <https://www2.acom.ucar.edu/acresp/forecasts-and-near-real-time-nrt-products> for both WRF-Chem and WACCM forecasts.

4.2.3.3. Data provision

For this module, WP3 is responsible for providing the dust and fire forecast model data.

4.2.4. Module 4 - Fracking analysis

The purpose of this module is to provide information on the expected impact of fracking activities on the air quality in the area of fracking. As opposed to the other modules in the AQ-WATCH system, this module is not real time and is rather a simulation on demand tool, i.e., when a user will wish to analyse a specific location, he/she will provide the location of the planned fracking activity and an offline analysis will be done. For this module, we are demonstrating the abilities of the tool for a specific region (Front range CO USA) and showing the impact on sensitive locations (e.g. hospitals, schools).

4.2.4.1. Module 4 specification

- **Grid resolution**
 - 4 km
- **Product availability**
 - Front range, Colorado
- **Type of data:**
 - Simulations with all emissions and simulations where certain emission sectors were zeroed out (O&G, traffic, industry, CEM)
- **Forecast time resolution**
 - Hourly data
- **Forecast Data refresh rate**
 - Upon request by the user
- **How far back does the model go?**
 - 4 weeks of 2014
- **How far ahead does the model go?**
 - Hindcasts for mid-July to mid-August 2014
- **Pollutant types:**
 - O₃ (hourly plus MDA8)
 - PM_{2.5} (hourly plus 24-hr average)
 - Benzene, Toluene, other VOC, NO_x, Ethane, Propane, HCHO
 - potentially ethane emissions to indicate the locations of O&G emissions
- **Data sources:**
 - WRF-CMAQ model (see report for download from <https://www2.acom.ucar.edu/frappe>), aircraft- and/or ground-based observations from the FRAPPE campaign to visualize

4.2.4.2. Data provision

For this module, WP4 is responsible for providing the forecast model data.

5. Dissemination and uptake

5.1. Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

5.2. This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

Although the content of this deliverable is public, it will be mainly used by AQ-WATCH partners and prime users, as described in the proposal. The product specification will be discussed with all partners and will be presented to prime users as part of the interactive process (the “Spiral Process” – see Section 1) in order to further develop those products.

6. Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

Yes No

Justification: We have had intense discussions about this deliverable. In order for all involved to be satisfied with the deliverable, these discussions took longer than originally planned. In agreement with EC, we have delayed the submission by 2 months. This delay will have no impact in further developments in the project.

7. Sustainability

Not relevant

8. Full track of dissemination activities

Not relevant

9. Full track of publications and IP

Not relevant

List of Acronyms

ACERA -Unconventional Renewable Energies Trade Association

AOD - Aerosol Optical Depth

BC - Black Carbon

CAMS - Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring System

DNI - Direct Normal Irradiance

GDP - Gross Domestic Product

GHI - Global Horizontal Irradiation

IPCC - Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

NGO - Non-Governmental Organization

OC - Organic Carbon

PM - Particulate Matter